

POCl₃-mediated synthesis of 2-*N*-arylimino-4-chloro-3-dichloromethylcoumarin and its conversion into 6*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]quinolin-6-one[†]

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Abstract : On heating in POCl₃, 2-(*N*-aryl)aminochromone-3-carbaldehyde produced 2-*N*-arylimino-4-chloro-3-dichloromethylcoumarin, which undergoes selective acid-catalyzed hydrolysis of its imino function to produce 4-chloro-3-dichloromethylcoumarin. The hydrolyzed product was transformed into 6*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]quinolin-6-one by reaction with aromatic primary amines.

Keywords : 2-Aminochromone, iminocoumarin, benzopyranoquinoline, POCl₃, *gem*-dihalide.

Introduction

A large number of naturally occurring compounds possess chromone and/or coumarin as the core structural unit¹. Apart from their natural abundance chromone and coumarin are also important for their diverse medicinal activity and both of them have been recognized as a privilege structure in drug discovery². Chromone and coumarin derivatives have been found to possess antimicrobial³, antitumor⁴ and antiviral⁵ activities. Coumarin derivatives with fluorescent property have been used in many applications in biology, medical analysis, lasers, sensors, nonlinear optical chromophores and electroluminescent materials⁶. Chromone-based chemosensor⁷ and molecular receptor⁸ have also been reported. The iminocoumarin-derived fluorophores are known for their high fluorescence ability and are widely used in organic electroluminescence devices and fluorescent probes⁹. Hg²⁺-selective chromogenic sensors have been developed based on iminocoumarin skeleton¹⁰. Besides their applications in pharmaceutical and material science, chromone and coumarin derivatives have also great synthetic importance due to their reactivity towards nucleophiles which provides a useful route for the synthesis of various new heterocyclic systems¹¹.

Earlier reports from our laboratory revealed that on

heating with POCl₃, 3-(arylaminoethylene)chroman-2,4-dione produced 4-arylamino-3-formylcoumarin at 60–70 °C, but 6-oxo-6*H*-1-benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]quinolines at 100 °C¹². Again on heating with POCl₃ at 60–80 °C, 2-aminochromones produced 4-chlorocoumarin¹³ and 3,3'-methylene-di-(2-arylamino-4*H*-chromen-4-one) produced 6,8-diarylimino-7*H*-pyrano[3,2-*c*:5,6-*c'*]dicoumarin¹⁴. In continuation of our studies on 2-(*N*-aryl)aminochromone-3-carbaldehyde¹⁵, we became interested to synthesise 4-chlorocoumarin-3-carbaldehyde, a very good precursor for the synthesis of many 3,4-fused coumarins¹⁶, from 2-(*N*-aryl)aminochromone-3-carbaldehyde.

Results and discussion

On heating 2-(*N*-phenyl)aminochromone-3-carbaldehyde (**1a**, R = H) in POCl₃ at 60–80 °C, the reaction mixture produced 3-dichloromethyl-2-*N*-phenyliminocoumarin **2a** in good yield (Scheme 1) (Table 1, entry 1).

Structure of **2a** was established on the basis of ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral analysis. Presence of nine aromatic protons in the ¹H NMR spectrum of **2a** indicates the survival of *N*-aryl moiety and a singlet at δ 7.72 indicates the conversion of CHO group to CHCl₂ group. The mass spectrum exhibited peaks of M, M+2,

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1

Table 1. Reaction of 1 with POCl₃

Entry	1			Time (h)	Product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
	R	R ¹	R ²				
1	H	H	H	3	2a	70	112-114
2	H	Me	H	3	2b	68	116-118
3	H	H	Me	3	2c	72	144-146
4	H	Me	Me	3	2d	69	166-168
5	Me	H	H	1	3a	56	122-124
6	Me	H	Me	1	3a	52	122-124
7	Me	Me	Me	1	3b	54	168-170

M+4 and M+6 in 10 : 9 : 3 : 0.4 ratios, which supports the presence of three chlorine atoms in 2a. The reaction was extended with different substituents on 1 to produce 2b-d (entries 2-4). The structures of 2 were further confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction study of 2b (Table 2) (Fig. 1). Formation of *gem*-dichloromethyl group from an aldehyde function using POCl₃ during the formation of 2 from 1 is an interesting observation. Literature survey revealed that formation of *gem*-dichloride derivative from carbonyl function has previously been achieved by PCl₅¹⁷, PhCCl₃/FeCl₃¹⁸, SeO₂/Me₃SiCl¹⁹, SOCl₂/DMF²⁰, SOCl₂/(Me₂N)₃PO²¹, BCl₃²² and (PhO)₃P/Cl₂²³. All these reagents are either costly or complex in nature. To check any role of 2-arylamino function in 1 for the formation of *gem*-dichloro compound 2, 3-formyl-6-methylchromone (5) was heated in POCl₃ at 60-80 °C for 3 h and interestingly it produced *gem*-dichloro compound 6 in 80% yield (Scheme 2).

On heating compound 2 (0.5 mmol) in methanol

Scheme 2

containing two drops of concentrated HCl acid, the imino-function of 2 was hydrolysed selectively to produce 3 along with a small amount of 4¹² (5-10%) (Scheme 1). Structure of compound 3a was assigned on the basis of ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral analysis. In the mass spectrum of 3a, the base peak appeared after the elimination of one molecule of HCl from 3a. The presence of two chlorine atoms in the base peak is supported by 10 : 6.5 : 1 ratio of the associated peaks. Finally the structure was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction study of 3a (Table 2) (Fig. 2).

It was anticipated that compound 3 may directly be obtained from the tertiary amine 1 (R = Me). With that

Fig. 1. ORTEP diagram of 2b.

tural resemblance with 4-chloro-3-formylcoumarin. Recently, 4-chloro-3-(trifluoroacetyl)- and 4-chloro-3-(methoxalyl)-coumarins have been utilised for the synthesis of a variety of 3,4-heteroannulated coumarins²⁴. So, it was of interest to check whether compound **3** having an electron deficient CHCl₂ group at its C-3 position can also be used as a synthon for 3,4-heteroannulated coumarins. Interestingly, heating compound **3a** with aniline (**7**, R³ = H) in methanol produced benzopyranoquinoline **8a**²⁵ in 68% yield (Scheme 3). Formation of **8** can be explained by a sequential Michael addition-elimination reaction (→**9**), followed by an intramolecular electrophilic cyclization and elimination of HCl. Similarly compounds **8b**, **8c** and **8d** were produced in moderate to good yields. Compounds **8a-d** were identical in all respects with the previously reported compounds¹².

Table 2. Crystal data of compounds **2b** and **3a**

	Compound 2b	Compound 3a
Empirical formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ Cl ₃ NO	C ₁₀ H ₅ Cl ₃ O ₂
Formula weight	352.63	263.49
Wavelength	0.71073 Å	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	triclinic	monoclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
Unit cell dimensions	<i>a</i> = 9.2084(9) Å, α = 62.689(11)° <i>b</i> = 9.5309(11) Å, β = 85.460(8)° <i>c</i> = 10.0734(9) Å, γ = 82.562(9)°	<i>a</i> = 13.5467(3) Å, α = 90.00° <i>b</i> = 5.43179(15) Å, β = 96.384(2)° <i>c</i> = 13.9382(3) Å, γ = 90.00°
Volume	778.73(14) Å ³	1019.25(4) Å ³
Z	2	4
Density (calcd.)	1.504 g/cm ³	1.717 g/cm ³
Absorption coefficient	0.588 μ	0.870 μ
<i>F</i> (000)	360	528
Crystal size	0.23 × 0.21 × 0.03 mm ³	0.6 × 0.2 × 0.2 mm ³
Theta range for data collection	3.11–30.00°	2.94–29.06°
Limiting indices	−12 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 9, −10 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 13, −14 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 13	−18 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 15, −3 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 7, −15 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17
Diffraction reflection unique	4346/3041	4879/2350
Reflections collected/unique	<i>R</i> _{int} = 0197	<i>R</i> _{int} = 0195
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.911	0.930
Reflection threshold	<i>R</i> ¹ = 0.0402	<i>R</i> ¹ = 0.0356
[<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>wR</i> ² = 0.0933	<i>wR</i> ² = 0.1195

intention **1a** (R=H) was methylated with methyl iodide and the resultant methylated product **1a** (R = Me) was heated with POCl₃. Interestingly, the reaction mixture produced **3a** in moderate yields. Compound **3a** has a struc-

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have reported the conversion of 2-*N*-arylaminochromone-3-carbaldehyde (**1**) to 2-*N*-arylimino-4-chloro-3-dichloromethylcoumarin (**2**) by POCl₃. To the

Fig. 2. ORTEP diagram of 3a.

Scheme 2

best of our knowledges conversion of aldehyde function to dichloromethyl group by POCl₃ is the first example in the literature. Compound **2** was selectively hydrolyzed to **3**, which produced **8** when treated with aromatic amine **7**. In the later conversion dichloromethyl group acted as a masked formyl group. Structures of compounds **2b** and **3a** were confirmed by X-ray crystallography²⁶.

Experimental

All reagents were purchased from commercial sources and used as such unless stated otherwise. The products were purified by column chromatography over silica gel (100–200). The recorded m.p.s are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Beckman IR 20a, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra in CDCl₃ on a Bruker 300 MHz and 75 MHz spectrometer, respectively. Mass spectra were recorded on a Qtof Micro YA 263 instrument and elemental analysis on a Perkin-Elmer 240c elemental analyzer. Light petroleum refers to the fraction with boiling range 60–80 °C.

General procedure for the reaction of 2-(N-aryl)amino-chromone-3-carbaldehyde (1, R = H) with POCl₃:

A solution of **1** (R = H) (0.5 mmol) in POCl₃ (2 ml) was heated with stirring at 60–80 °C for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into crushed ice (100 g). The separated yellow solid was filtered out, washed with water, dried in air and recrystallized from light petroleum to obtain **2** as yellow crystalline solid.

4-Chloro-3-dichloromethyl-2-(N-phenyl)imino-2H-1-benzopyran (2a):

Yellow crystalline solid, yield : 118 mg (70%); m.p. 112–114 °C; IR : 761, 1590, 1628, 2905, 3054 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 7.03 (1H, br d, *J* 8.1 Hz, 8-H), 7.15 (1H, br t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 4'-H), 7.22–7.26 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.34–7.36 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.72 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.85 (1H, br d, *J* 7.8 Hz, 5-H); ¹³C NMR : δ 64.2, 115.6, 118.6, 122.9, 124.3, 124.6, 125.7, 126.2, 128.7, 129.4, 132.8, 144.6, 145.0, 151.6; ms : *m/z* 338 (M + H⁺, 100%), 340 (M + 2 + H⁺, 98%), 342 (M + 4 + H⁺, 32%), 344 (M + 6 + H⁺, 6%), 360 (M + Na⁺, 60%), 362 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 55%), 364 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 20%), 366 (M + 6 + Na⁺, 2%) (Found : C, 56.72; H, 3.01; N, 4.18. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₀Cl₃NO : C, 56.75; H, 2.98; N, 4.14%).

4-Chloro-3-dichloromethyl-2-(N-phenyl)imino-6-methyl-2H-1-benzopyran (2b):

Yellow crystalline solid, yield : 119 mg (68%); m.p. 116–118 °C; IR : 756, 1557, 1630, 2915, 3032 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 2.38 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.92 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.14 (1H, br t, *J* 7.2 Hz, 4'-H), 7.21–7.24 (3H, m, Ar-H), 7.33–7.38 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.62 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.72 (1H, br s, 5-H); ms : *m/z* 352 (M + H⁺, 100%), 354 (M + 2 + H⁺, 98%), 356 (M + 4 + H⁺, 32%), 358 (M + 6 + H⁺, 8%), 374 (M + Na⁺, 60%), 376 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 58%), 378 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 18%), 380 (M + 6 + Na⁺, 2%) (Found : C, 57.92; H, 3.37; N, 4.01. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂Cl₃NO : C, 57.90; H, 3.43; N, 3.97%).

4-Chloro-3-dichloromethyl-2-N-(p-tolyl)imino-2H-1-benzopyran (2c):

Yellow crystalline solid, yield : 126 mg (72%); m.p. 144–146 °C; IR : 764, 1580, 1639, 2928, 3035 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 2.37 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.06 (1H, br d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.10–7.26 (5H, m, Ar-H), 7.40–7.47 (1H, m, Ar-H), 7.73 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.87 (1H, dd, *J* 7.8, 0.9 Hz, 5-

H) (Found : C, 57.88; H, 3.36; N, 3.92. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₂Cl₃NO : C, 57.90; H, 3.43; N, 3.97%).

4-Chloro-3-dichloromethyl-2-*N*-(*p*-tolyl)imino-6-methyl-2*H*-1-benzopyran (2d) :

Yellow crystalline solid, yield : 126 mg (69%); m.p. 166–168 °C; IR : 762, 1571, 1635, 2919, 3020 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 2.36 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.95 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, 8-H), 7.12–7.20 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.24 (1H, br d, *J* 8.7 Hz, 7-H), 7.63 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.74 (1H, br s, 5-H); mass : *m/z* 366 (M + H⁺, 100%), 368 (M + 2 + H⁺, 97%), 370 (M + 4 + H⁺, 32%), 372 (M + 6 + H⁺, 3%), 388 (M + Na⁺, 55%), 390 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 50%), 392 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 10%), 394 (M + 6 + Na⁺, 2%) (Found : C, 58.88; H, 3.86; N, 3.91. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₄Cl₃NO : C, 58.96; H, 3.85; N, 3.82%).

Treatment of 6-methylchromone-3-carboxaldehyde (5) with POCl₃ :

Aldehyde **5** (94 mg, 0.5 mmol) was heated in POCl₃ (2 ml) at 60–80 °C for 3 h. The resultant solution was cooled and poured in ice-water (50 g). The deposited solid was filtered, washed with water, dried in air and recrystallised from benzene-light petroleum to afford **6**.

3-Dichloromethyl-6-methylchromone (6) :

White crystalline solid, yield : 95 mg (78%); m.p. 152–154 °C; IR : 793, 1553, 1692, 2827, 3054 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 2.47 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.04 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.40 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, 8-H), 7.53 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 1.8 Hz, 7-H), 8.02 (1H, br s, 5-H), 8.47 (1H, s, 2-H); ms : *m/z* 265 (M + Na⁺, 100%), 267 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 65%), 269 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 10%) (Found : C, 54.24; H, 3.28. Calcd. for C₁₁H₈Cl₂O₂ : C, 54.35; H, 3.32%).

General procedure for hydrolysis of 2 :

To a methanolic solution (25 ml) of **2** (0.5 mmol), two drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added and the resultant mixture was heated under reflux for 1 h. The solvent from the reaction mixture was removed under reduced pressure and ice water (50 g) was added to the concentrate. The resultant oily mass was extracted with CHCl₃, the organic layer was washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and subjected to column chromatography. Compound **3** was obtained as white solid when 50% light petroleum in benzene was used as eluent and compound **4** was obtained as pale yellow solid when eluted

with benzene. Compounds **4a** (6%), **4b** (10%), **4c** (5%) and **4d** (6%) were found to be identical in all respect with the authentic samples¹².

4-Chloro-3-(dichloromethyl)-2*H*-chromen-2-one (3a) :

White crystalline solid; yield : 70 mg (53%); m.p. 122–124 °C; IR : 783, 1555, 1735, 2935, 3048 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 7.30 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.37–7.46 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.64–7.72 (1H, m, Ar-H), 8.00 (1H, br d, *J* 7.8 Hz, 5-H); ¹³C NMR : δ 63.6, 116.8, 116.9, 123.6, 125.3, 126.6, 134.3, 134.4, 152.0, 166.0; ms : *m/z* 285 (M+Na⁺, 10%), 287 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 8%), 289 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 3%), 227 (M – HCl + H⁺, 100%), 229 (M – HCl + 2 + H⁺, 65%), 231 (M – HCl + 4 + H⁺, 14%) (Found : C, 45.68; H, 1.95. Calcd. for C₁₀H₅Cl₃O₂ : C, 45.58; H, 1.91%).

4-Chloro-3-(dichloromethyl)-6-methyl-2*H*-chromen-2-one (3b) :

White crystalline solid; yield : 80 mg (58%); m.p. 168–170 °C; IR : 787, 1564, 1740, 2923, 3051 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR : δ 2.48 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.26 (1H, s, CHCl₂), 7.28 (1H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, 8-H), 7.48 (1H, br d, *J* 9.0 Hz, 7-H), 7.76 (1H, br s, 5-H); ms : *m/z* 299 (M + Na⁺, 70%), 301 (M + 2 + Na⁺, 67%), 303 (M + 4 + Na⁺, 25%), 305 (M + 6 + Na⁺, 4%), 277 (M + H⁺, 12%), 279 (M + 2 + H⁺, 10%), 281 (M + 4 + H⁺, 3%), 241 (M – HCl + H⁺, 100%), 243 (M – HCl + 2 + H⁺, 70%), 245 (M – HCl + 4 + H⁺, 13%) (Found : C, 47.69; H, 2.61. Calcd. for C₁₁H₇Cl₃O₂ : C, 47.60; H, 2.54%).

General procedure for the synthesis of 3 from 1 (R = Me) :

A solution of **1** (R = Me) (0.5 mmol) in POCl₃ (2 ml) was heated with stirring at 60–80 °C for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled to room temperature and poured into crushed ice (100 g). The separated solid was filtered, washed with water, dried in air and purified by column chromatography. Compounds **3a** (53%) and **3b** (58%) were obtained as white solid when 50% light-petroleum in benzene was used as eluent. Compounds **3a** and **3b** were found to be identical in all respects with the compounds obtained by hydrolysis of **2a** and **2b**, respectively.

General procedure for the synthesis of 6*H*-[1]benzopyrano[4,3-*b*]quinolin-6-one (8) :

Aromatic amine **7** (0.5 mmol) was added to a

methanolic solution (25 ml) of **3** (0.5 mmol) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 1 h. Solvent from reaction mixture was removed under reduced pressure and the resulted residue was dissolved in benzene, washed with water, dried over Na₂SO₄ and recrystallized from benzene-light petroleum (70 : 30) to obtain **8a** (68%), **8b** (72%), **8c** (65%), **8d** (70%) as white crystalline solids. The compounds were found to be identical in all respects with those obtained by the reaction of 3-arylamino(methylidene)chroman-2,5-dione with POCl₃.¹²

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26. The structures were solved and refined using SHELXL-97 suite of programs²⁷. Crystallographic data for this structure have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre and allocated deposition numbers are CCDC 895742 (for **2b**) and 895743 (for **3a**). These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>.
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